

Variation of Directive Speech act of Stephen Hawking in *the Theory of Everything* Movie

Cindilla Agustian

(English Literature Department, Gunadarma University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT :As social being, we used language as a tool to communicate and interact with others. Through communication people can convey what she or he trying to say such as giving information, asking something, express an idea and opinion, etc. When someone speaks, every word, phrase, or sentence she or he utters are not just utterances without meaning, however it can perform action through the utterances. The action through utterance called speech acts. This study investigates the variation of directive speech act by examining the utterance produce by Stephen Hawking in *The Theory of Everything* film as the primary data. In analyzing and interpreting the data, qualitative method applies to this study. A total variation of directive speech act is 19 data. The result shows there are only three variations performed, command (10 times or 53%), request (7 times or 37%), and suggestion (2 times or 10%). Command being the most dominant used by Stephen Hawking.

KEYWORDS -directive speech acts, film, utterances

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

Communication is an absolute thing without exception, along with the nature of humans as social beings. We used language as a tool to communicate and interact with each other. Through communication one can convey what she or he wants to convey or mean to someone, such as expressing an idea or opinion, sharing information, asking something, suggesting, etc.. Sapir (1921) in Rohmah (2020, p. 19) stated that "Language is as purely human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions, and desire by means of systems of voluntarily produced symbol." [1]. One of the conditions for communication that can be established is if there is a harmony between the speaker and the hearer and they share the same language. When someone speaks, every word, phrase, or sentence she or he utters are not just utterances without meaning, however, it can perform action through the utterances. Each of those utterances produced by the speaker performs different implicit actions or meanings depending on the intention of the hearer. An action in verbal communication has a message in itself, so the communication is not only about language but also with action (Bach & Hamish, 1979, p. 153) [2]. The action that is performed through the speech is called a speech act. Speech acts refer to the use of language based on context

1.2. Relevant Researches

Regarding the speech acts, studies with the same topic have been already conducted by Tutuarima, Nuraeningsih, & Rusiana (2018) entitled "An Analysis of Speech Act Used in London Has Fallen Movie" [4]. In their study, they discussed the kinds of speech act used in London Has Fallen Movie and the way of speech act and the classifications of illocutionary act used in London Has Fallen Movie. The method used in this study is descriptive qualitative. Through the analysis in this study, it can be concluded that the most common kind of speech act is an illocutionary act, with the directive and expressive being the most dominant used.

Following Tutuarima, Nuraeningsih, & Rusiana (2018), Akinwotu (2013) carried out a study entitled "A Speech Act Analysis of the Acceptance of Nomination Speeches of Chief Obafemi Awolowo and Chief M. K. O. Abiola" [5]. This study is aimed to investigate the role of language in the communication and interpretation of intentions by examining selected political speeches as pieces of discourse. The result of the study revealed that the acceptance of nomination speeches are characterized by illocutionary speech acts with assertives, expressives and commissive acts mostly used as mobilization strategy to achieve persuasion.

Another study related to speech act is Rohmah (2020) with "An Analysis of Assertive Acts in Letters to Juliet Movie" [1]. This study generally discusses the use of assertive illocutionary acts uttered by the main character in Letters to Juliet Movie. To conduct this study, the researcher used a descriptive quantitative approach. Results to this study showed that there are seven types of assertive acts: informing, complaining, arguing, explaining, reporting, asserting, and retelling with reporting act as the dominant. The speaker tends to use reporting in order to report something that has been heard, seen, done, or felt to the hearer that does not yet know. Moreover, the formal pattern that the speaker used in reporting acts is positive and negative verbal form, positive and negative nominal form, and question tag form.

From the three relevant studies above, it is revealed that analyzing speech acts is not limited to the utterances that we say in our daily communication, but also through other media such as film. All studies need limitations in order to avoid an enlarged discussion that is far from aspects relevant. With limitations, the researcher can focus to analyze the items under investigation. Related to the statement above, this study is limited to the directive speech act.

1.3. Purpose of the Study

This study aimed to analyze the variation of directive speech act in conversation carried out by Stephen Hawking as the main character with other characters in the film entitled *The Theory of Everything*. The research is interested in conducting research by using Yule's theory of directive speech act.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A speech act is a verbal action through utterances. Yule (1996, p. 47) has theorized speech act as the action performed through utterances. Speech act concerned with the way in which words can be used not only to give information but to carry action too [3]. We perform a speech act in our real-life interaction when we offer something like an apology, commanding, suggesting, warning, promising, complaining, inviting, greeting, requesting, etc. Speech act may contain only one word, like for the example, "Hi!", or it can be a clause or sentence, "Hi, Jane. Want to join my party?". Through speech acts, the speakers try to convey the intent and purpose of communicating to their hearer, with the expectation the hearer understands what the speaker's meant. In speech acts, it does not only focus on the sentence in an utterance or conversation between the speaker and hearer, the context also takes a part in it since the utterance or conversation cannot be separated among activities, situation, topic, code, and conversation. In short, speech acts are actions carried out by someone as a reflection from one's speech or utterance that is intended to make the hearer do something.

Those performing action by producing utterances covers in three related acts by Yule (1996, pp. 48-49), namely locutionary act (an act of saying something), illocutionary act (an act of doing something), and perlocutionary act (an act of affecting something). Furthermore, Yule (1996, pp. 53-54) goes to works on five basic categories of illocutionary speech act: declarations, representatives, expressives, directive, and commissive. From the five categories of speech act, it can be used to analyzed the intend meaning of what the speaker's utterances.

- Declaration
Declaration are those kinds of speech acts that change the world via their utterance.
- Representatives
Representatives are those kinds of speech acts that state what the speaker believes to be the case or not. Statement of fact, assertions, conclusion, and descriptions are all the examples.

- Expressives
Expressives are those kinds of speech acts that state what the speaker feels. They express psychological states and can be statement of pleasure, pain, likes, dislikes, joy, or sorrow. In using a directive, the speaker attempt to make the world fit the words via the hearer.
- Directive
Directive speech act is a kind of speech acts that speakers use to get someone else to do something. They express what the speaker wants by using commands, orders, request, and suggestions.
- Commisive
Commisive are those kinds of speech acts that speakers use to commit themselves to some future action. They express what the speaker intends. They are promises, threats, refusals, and pledges. In using a commissive, the speaker undertakes to make the world fit the words (via the speaker).

In this study, the researcher chooses directive speech act as the main focus. We often used directive speech act in our daily communication life. However, some miss understanding sometimes occurs between the speaker and the hearer, making the message is not conveyed properly. Thus, it is necessary to learn about speech acts.

III. METHODOLOGY

In doing this research, the method employed by the researcher is the qualitative method. The term qualitative according to Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault (2016, p. 7) refers in the broadest sense to research that produces descriptive data—people’s own written or spoken words and observable behavior [6]. Corbin and Strauss (2008) stated, “Qualitative is a process of examining and interpreting data to elicit meaning, gain understanding, and develop empirical knowledge” (p. 1)[7]. Another definition comes from Creswell (2014), who has theorized, “Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individual or groups ascribe to a social or human problem.” [8]. In line with the definitions, the researcher used qualitative as a method since the data collected in this study are in the forms of words and in a description way, also the subject of this study is a human utterance as the instrument.

The object of this study used the film entitled The Theory of Everything. The Theory of Everything is a film directed by James Marsh, this film’s first premiere at USA on November 7, 2014. The utterance contains the directive speech act produced by Stephen Hawking as the primary data of this study. The data to be analyzed are taken from random sampling.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data of this study has been collected and analyzed by the researcher. There are four variations of directive speech act based on Yule’s (1996); command, request, suggestion, and warning. The directive speech act is a kind of speech act in which the speaker is saying something and intends the hearer to carry out an action or do something. The researcher found out there are only three variations of the directive speech act presented by Stephen Hawking, they are command (10 times or 53%), request (7 times or 37%), suggestion (2 times or 10%). Warning is not performed by him. Total to this variation of directive speech act is 19 data.

Directive Speech Act	Frequency	Percentage
Command	10 times	53%
Request	7 times	37%
Suggestion	2 times	10%
Warning	0 times	0%
Total	19 times	

Table 1. Summary of the forms of directive speech act

Variation of Directive Speech Act

Figure 1. Percentage of the forms of directive speech act

a. Command

Context of the situation: Stephen entered the seminar room and handed over two trains timetables on the table. Other students help him by push the timetables down the desk to Mr. Sciamia, who picks them up.

Sample of the datum

Mr. Sciamia : “Right. Trains timetables?”
Stephen : “Ah...”
Mr. Schiama : “That’s, uh, totally unacceptable. These expired a month ago.”
Stephen : “**It’s on the back, I had a little accident.**”
Mr. Schiama : “Ah...”

This conversation happens between Stephen and Mr. Schiama when Stephen entered the seminar room where his friend and Ph.D. Supervisor, Mr. Schiama is gathered. The bolded utterance is considered as command since Stephen order Mr. Schiama to turn over the timetables filled with the formulas and calculations of the assignment he gave, marked by the utterance “It’s on the back, ...” and Mr. Schiama doing what Stephen’s command to him, that turns the timetables over and looks at the answer. The speech acts fulfilled due to Stephen as addressor trying to convey his intent and Mr. Schiama as addressee carrying an action.

b. Request

Context of the situation: Stephen went to the pub with his friend then steeped to the bar and asked the bartender to refill on his drink.

Sample of the datum

Stephen : “**Can I get two more of those, please?**”
Bartender : “yeah, sure.”

Stephen went to the pub together with his friend. Brian, Rees, Ellis, and Carter are playing Pinball, meanwhile, Stephen watches and drinks a beer. And then, Stephen steeped to the bar and asks the bartender to refill on his beer. From the conversation in the datum above, the bolded utterance produced by Stephen is considered as a request. It can be seen from the utterance “Can I get two more of those, please?”. The speech acts is fulfill. Stephen as addressor try to convey his intention by request to the bartender to refill his beer and make it two, and the bartender as the addresses carries an action by doing what Stephen’s asks to him.

c. Suggestion

Context of the situation: Jane puts pillow behind Stephen who almost slept in the bed. Stephen opens a conversation with her because he see Jane look stress

Sample of the datum

Stephen : **“I understand if you need help. If someone is prepared to offer it, I won’t object”**

Jane seems stressed and struggling to share her focus on taking care of Stephen and their children. Stephen, who feels sorry for Jane, opens a conversation and lets Jane consider hiring someone to help her look after the children. Jane’s face looks happy to hear that. The datum “I understand if you need help. If someone is prepared to offer it, I won’t object” is suggesting the statement of the directive speech act. The speech acts is fulfilled. Stephen as addressor tries to convey his intention by suggesting Jane hire someone to help her, and Jane as the addressee carry an action by doing what Stephen’s suggests to her. Jane asks Jonathan, her Choir Master in the church choir, to help her teach and look after her children.

V. CONCLUSION

This study has examines utterance performed by Stephen Hawking as the primary data to be analyzed. The researcher find out there are three variation of directive speech act performed by Stephen Hawking in *The Theory of Everything* film. The table and diagram in the previous chapter revealed the total frequency of variation of directive speech act, namely 19 times: command (10 times or 53%), request (7 times or 37%), and suggestion (2 times or 10%). The researcher does not find warning performed by Stephen Hawking. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the most common directive speech acts used is command.

VI. Acknowledgements

All praise to God for His blessing, so I can complete this article, Variation of Directive Speech Act of Stephen Hawking in *The Theory of Everything* Movie. I would like also to thank to my family and lecturers for their support and assistance in writing this article.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. F. Rohmah, An analysis of asserive acts in letters to Juliet movie. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 25(4), 2020, 19-27.
- [2] K. Bach, and R. M. Hamish, *Linguistic communication and speech acts*. (Cambridge: Mass: MIT Press, 1979).
- [3] G. Yule, *Pragmatics*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996).
- [4] Z. Tutuarima, Nuraeningsih, and Rusiana. An analysis of speech act used in London has fallen movie. *Vision: Journal for Language and Foreign Language Learning*, 7(2), 2018, 122-131.
- [5] S. A. Akinwotu, A speech act analysis of the acceptance of nomination speeches of Chief Obafemi Awolowo and Chief M. K. O. Abiola. *English Linguistics Research*, 2(1), 2013, 43-51.
- [6] S. J. Taylor, R. Bogdan, and M. L. DeVault, *Introduction to qualitative research method*. (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2016).
- [7] J. Corbin, and A. Strauss, *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. (London: SAGE Publications, 2008).
- [8] J. W. Creswell, *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (4th Ed.)*. (London: SAGE Publications, 2014).